
Biochar: Contributions to Sustainable Agriculture, Climate Change, and The Circular Economy

Kabita Budthapa¹, Dr. I.P. Handayani²

^{1,2}Hutson School of Agriculture, Murray State University, USA

¹ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-6064-3664>

ABSTRACT: Global warming, soil health management, and the adoption of sustainable green technology are among the major issues of the century. Biochar offers significant potential to address these problems and is an essential instrument for achieving sustainable development objectives. This article aims to thoroughly investigate the potential of biochar as a sustainable method for managing agricultural waste, as well as its role in enhancing soil quality, mitigating climate change, and promoting circular economy integration. It highlights how biochar can enhance the soil's physical, chemical, and biological properties, thereby boosting microbial activity, water retention, nutrient availability, and ultimately, agricultural productivity. Biochar's capacity to sequester carbon, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and support carbon credit markets is also discussed. Notwithstanding these advantages, technical constraints, legal obstacles, and economic feasibility remain major impediments to widespread implementation. The review highlights the need for supportive policies and standardized frameworks while identifying research gaps in biochar stability, environmental impact, and application techniques. This study presents biochar as a flexible, scalable technology with broad applications in global climate resilience and sustainable land management.

KEYWORDS: Biochar, Climate change, Soil fertility, Waste management

1. INTRODUCTION

Global warming, wastewater treatment, soil health management, and the adoption of sustainable green technology are among the major issues of the twenty-first century (Bano, et al., 2025). The world's energy demand is rising due to population growth. Energy is needed in every area of the nation (Yaashikaa, et al., 2019). Fossil fuels are considered a major source of energy in the modern world. However, the need to replace fossil fuels has arisen due to the environmental impact of CO₂ and global energy concerns (Gollakota, et al., 2018). Agricultural waste has been the focus of extensive research for more than 60 years due to its potential to be converted into useful resources (Kumar et al., 2023). As agricultural productivity increases, this waste stream continues to expand. This has negative effects on ecological and human health (Howell, et al., 2021). Biochar, a carbonaceous residue of the pyrolysis process, can be used to sustainably achieve and protect water, soil, and air across major industrial activities and in agricultural operations (Zabaniotou & Stamou, 2020). Biochar is widely recognized for its ability to eliminate pollutants, make a substantial contribution to the fight against climate change, and generate bioenergy. The concept of the "circular economy" is quickly gaining acceptance for its primary objective of reducing waste through careful planning. Because of its adaptability in lowering waste and improving the effectiveness of the circular economy, biochar has recently become a key contributor to the environmental community (Bano, et al., 2025).

1.1 Biochar contribution to soil health and quality

Land deterioration is one of the main problems with soil. Biochar technology is compatible with contemporary green development concepts such as sustainable development, reduced carbon emissions, and environmental protection. Biochar technology helps prevent soil contamination, protect the environment, maintain ecosystem balance, promote a positive feedback loop, and support the sustainable growth of the agricultural environment (Zhang et al., 2021). When biochar production and soil application are combined intentionally, several benefits result. These include better soil physical properties, greater nutrient availability and retention, and increased biological activity, which enhance agricultural yields and benefit society by reducing soil emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere.

1.2 Benefits of biochar on the physical properties of soil

The chemical and physical properties of the soil govern its water-holding capacity, aeration, and soil strength, all of which directly affect crop yields (Benjamin et al., 2003). The application of biochar enhanced soil porosity, although the extent of porosity varied

with soil type and the type of biochar used (Herath et al., 2013). The relative contributions of the three main types of pores to the overall increase in soil porosity vary with the amount of biochar and the soil type (Githinji, 2014). The elevated porosity of biochar increased soil porosity. Mukherjee and Lal (2013) found that the application of biochar reduced soil bulk density because it has a very high porosity, thereby increasing pore volume and decreasing bulk density. Githinji (2014), found that speeding up the application of biochar significantly decreased bulk density. Certain polysaccharides enhance the adherence of soil colloidal particles. Using biochar gives microorganisms a place to live while shielding them from predators and desiccation. The polysaccharides released by the bacteria promote soil agglomeration. Compared to the control treatment, the soil treated with biochar held 15% more moisture per (Laird, et al., 2010). Adding biochar to the soil improved its water retention, though results varied by texture. Applying biochar to sandy soils greatly increases the soil's water-holding capacity; in loamy soils, it has minimal impact; and in clay soils, it has no effect. Applying biochar improved soil water retention through its adsorptive properties and increased soil porosity (Herath et al., 2013). Hydrophilic functional groups were present on the graphene sheet's surface and in the pores of the biochar, as reported by Uzoma et al. (2010).

1.3 Benefits of Biochar on soil Chemical properties

The total impact of biochar on the chemical composition of soil. The addition of biochar has, on average, greatly improved all soil chemical characteristics (such as pH, electrical conductivity, cation exchange capacity, soil organic carbon, soil total carbon, and the soil's C:N ratio) across the entire dataset. Aside from the soil's pH and SOC, as well as the biochar's oxygen concentration. The biochar addition treatments also included additional characteristics that enhanced soil CEC, crop type, sand, silt, and clay content; initial soil pH; feedstock materials; pyrolysis temperature; biochar carbon and nitrogen content; and biochar C: N ratio. Soil CEC improved in the biochar addition treatments due to biochar carbon and the length of the trial (Singh et al., 2022). The addition of biochar increased soil pH, cation exchange capacity, and organic carbon by 46%, 20%, and 27%, respectively, with greater effects in coarse- and fine-textured soils (Singh et al., 2022).

1.4 Benefits of Biochar on soil biological properties

Biochar's strong interactions with minerals and soil organic matter make it a promising tool for improving soil microbial populations (Pokharel et al., 2020). Because of its capacity to reduce carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from soil organic components and its resilience to biotic and abiotic degradation, biochar has been strongly suggested as a means of improving soil carbon sinks. Because biochar is a labile carbon source, it stimulates significant microbial activity, which is the main driver of the rise in soil enzymatic activity following its application (Ouyang et al., 2014). However, it has been found that adding biochar increases microbial activity in soil by creating a more conducive environment for growth and development (Karhu et al., 2011). Warnock, et al. (2007) outlined how adding biochar affected mycorrhizal association. According to Shen, et al. (2016), there are four ways that char affects mycorrhizal association activity and abundance: (i) changing the physiochemical properties of the soil, which affects the availability of nutrients; (ii) changing the activities of soil organisms that indirectly affect mycorrhizae; (iii) detoxifying allelochemicals; and (iv) providing cover from soil predators. Each of these mechanisms boosts mycorrhizal colonization.

2. BIOCHAR CONTRIBUTION TO CARBON SEQUESTRATION AND CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION

2.1 Stability of biochar in soil

The biochar's stability in soil is determined by its resistance to degradation and how long it remains in the soil as a carbon source. Given its rates of breakdown and generally accepted stability, biochar can persist in soil for hundreds to thousands of years. Its distinctive chemical structure, characterized by high aromaticity and resistance to microbial degradation, is responsible for its stability. Fragrant OC and OC components stabilized by soil minerals made up the stable organic carbon (OC) of biochar. Biochar had at least two pools of organic carbon: labile and stable OC, per Han, et al. (2020). For instance, the terms "labile" and "stable" were used to describe OC with little and high resistance to mineralization, respectively. Numerous investigations are currently underway to determine whether biochar is stable or mineralized in soil (Fang et al., 2015). The primary determinants of biochar's ability to sequester carbon are its stability in soil and its stimulation of the mineralization of native soil organic carbon. A study by Yang et al. (2022) found that biochar produced at higher temperatures did, in fact, have tremendous potential for sequestering soil carbon and was more stable in clayey soils.

2.2 Biochar and greenhouse gas emissions

Biochar is a powerful organic additive that can help fight climate change and soil conservation for sustainable crop production. It originates from organic materials and results from anaerobic pyrolysis. It can lower greenhouse gas emissions from soil to the atmosphere and store carbon in the terrestrial ecosystem for a long time. Biochar was used to enhance soil health, increase carbon absorption and storage, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and raise crop yields, thereby supporting sustained soil health to meet the growing demand for food grains from the world's population (Kannan et al., 2013). It has been shown that Biochar-amended soils reduce phosphorus runoff into surface waters, nitrogen leaching into groundwater, and nitrous oxide emissions by 50–80%. Biochar field testing in Colombia showed a considerable drop in CH₄ emissions and an 80% reduction in N₂O emissions (Renner, 2007). A

study showed that biochar applications reduced N₂O emissions in grassland systems and soybean plantations by 50 and 80%, respectively (Rondon, et al., 2005).

3. CONTRIBUTION OF BIOCHAR FOR CARBON OFFSETS AND THE MARKET

3.1 Mechanisms of carbon stability

Biochar carbon offsets are a new segment of the voluntary carbon market. Burning biomass produces biochar, a substance that looks like charcoal and offers a sustainable carbon removal option. Businesses are increasingly buying biochar carbon credits to meet their net-zero goals, and the market is growing rapidly. Carbon stability over an extended period (100–1000 years), reduced emissions of nitrous oxide from the soil, and the stabilization and buildup of soil organic matter (Weng, et al., 2022). Among the climate benefits of biochar are the avoided greenhouse gas and fossil fuel emissions that would otherwise result from the breakdown of biomass (Leng & Huang, 2018). Depending on the type of stability inquiry, modeling, field and lab-based incubations, and/or instrumental analytical techniques are used to evaluate the stability of biochar carbon (Leng & Huang, 2018). The study's findings by Adhikari, et al. (2024) support the stability and durability of biochar carbon storage, making it a viable option for carbon dioxide removal. Compared with other production conditions, we conclude that the significant impact on biochar carbon stability was due to the feedstocks.

3.2 Carbon credit eligibility

Biochar has become a potential carbon offset option. To promote sustainable carbon dioxide sequestration, incorporate biochar into carbon trading schemes, and stimulate global investment in the biochar industry, biochar carbon credit requirements must be established in a practical and cost-effective manner. In line with sustainable development objectives, biochar is a flexible, scalable technology with the potential to make a substantial contribution to carbon credit generation. To fully explore biochar's potential to mitigate climate change, more research, openness, and international collaboration are needed (Salma et al., 2024). The goal of the carbon market is to make CO₂-equivalent (CO₂e) emissions a tradable commodity by assigning a price to each ton of emissions. This makes it possible to trade carbon emissions and carbon removals, often referred to as offsets.

In climate change mitigation and carbon credit markets, biochar has the potential to revolutionize the industry (Mulabagal et al., 2015). In doing so, biochar improves soil quality and agricultural productivity while removing CO₂ from the atmosphere (Babu et al., 2023). Biochar goes beyond the traditional carbon market, which is an exchange-based mechanism that assigns a monetary value to each ton of CO₂ emissions, by integrating emissions reduction and sustainable land use into a single framework (Sörman, 2023). In addition to lowering their carbon footprint, people, companies, and governments can improve soil fertility, support sustainable agriculture, and reduce environmental problems brought on by land degradation by producing biochar (Yadav & Ramakrishna, 2023).

Figure 1: Carbon sequestration brought on by biochar and its use in environmentally friendly and agriculturally sustainable management (Bano et al., 2025).

4. CIRCULAR ECONOMIC INTEGRATION

The idea of the "circular economy" is quickly gaining acceptance for its primary objective of reducing waste through careful planning. Because of its adaptability in lowering waste and improving the effectiveness of the circular economy, biochar has recently become a key contributor to the environmental community (Bano, et al., 2025).

4.1 Closed-loop system in biochar

A method in which materials are continuously recycled during the agricultural process is known as closed-loop agriculture. This model minimizes reliance on external inputs, maximizes resource utilization, and minimizes waste. Because it turns organic waste into a useful soil amendment that can increase agricultural productivity, biochar production is essential to this system. Crop leftovers, animal manure, and food processing waste are examples of organic agricultural residues that are diverted into biochar synthesis processes in a closed-loop value chain. The cycle is completed by reintroducing the produced biochar into the soil, replenishing the agricultural system with carbon and nutrients (Anon., 2024). In agricultural settings, biochar-based solutions can treat wastewater from both point and diffuse sources, potentially reducing water use and increasing crop yields. In addition to removing costly transportation costs, the on-farm production of biochar and its subsequent applications in a closed-loop agriculture system will also create a circular flow of materials and energy that promotes additional economic and environmental benefits because it can be made from crop residues and other biomass wastes (Li, et al., 2020).

4.2 Contribution of biochar to economic viability

Biochar's economic viability is a complicated topic with both advantages and disadvantages. The manufacture of biochar can be profitable in some circumstances, but it has drawbacks, such as high production costs and competition with conventional charcoal. However, when combined with laws and incentives that encourage its use, the advantages of biochar can outweigh these expenses. To ascertain the overall viability of biochar, these expenses must be balanced against the agronomic advantages of the material. Greenhouse gas (GHG) reductions in published studies assessing the emission mitigation potential of biochar range from -0.124 to 16 t CO₂e per ton of biochar applied, indicating a complex and variable impact (Nematian et al., 2021). This variation underscores the importance of considering factors such as crop species, soil type, and local climate when assessing biochar efficacy. Furthermore, to optimize its benefits and avoid potential drawbacks, incorporating biochar into current farming operations requires careful planning and adaptation (Ottani et al., 2024). Biochar provides more than simply immediate agronomic benefits from an economic perspective. Farmers can benefit from their environmental initiatives through possible participation in carbon markets (Patel & Panwar, 2024).

The creation of jobs, labor wages, value-added products, and gross output all show good economic growth, according to the regional economic analysis. When combined with governmental policy initiatives, the economic viability of a circular bioeconomy for waste orchard biomass is supported by stochastic cost estimates and net positive regional economic effects. The findings could contribute to the growth of circular bioeconomy for orchard biomass and biochar in the study area and globally (Nematian, et al., 2021). The high fixed and variable costs associated with natural monopolies have contributed to the industry's lack of profitability in biochar production (Skapa, 2012). It is difficult to recover costs and optimize the value of environmental advantages when market demand is low. Even though biochar is used in most households rather than charcoal (Vochozka, et al., 2016; Maroušek, et al., 2019). In many rural areas of Asia and Europe, biochar has been accepted (Olarieta, et al., 2011).

According to an analysis of financial indicators by Patel & Panwar (2024) related to biochar production, the operational expenditure (OPEX) was \$2339.40, the cost of feedstock was \$2420.25, and the cost of transportation was \$293.71. The cost of producing 1 ton of biochar was \$232.87, and labor accounted for 27.07 percent of the total manufacturing and application costs. According to the statistics, when biochar was sprayed at a rate of 12 tons/ha, the maximum yearly revenue from crop production (maize in the kharif season and peas in the rabi season) was \$525.88 per hectare. The expected value of carbon sequestration was \$186.6 per ton of biochar. Economic indicators showed that when 8 tons of biochar were applied per acre, the benefit-cost ratio (BCR) was at its maximum, at 1.476. At this rate, the internal rate of return (IRR) and net present value (NPV) simultaneously peaked at 85.71 percent and \$932.85, respectively (Patel & Panwar, 2024).

Figure 2: The cumulative density function displays the overall cost of biochar (Mg⁻¹) over the costs of labor, fuel, permits, and production volume (Nematian, et al., 2021).

5. CHALLENGES

5.1 Technical challenges in biochar production and application

Large-scale biochar manufacturing is hampered by several technical issues. These include environmental issues, regulatory barriers, production efficiency, and feedstock logistics. Other major obstacles are the energy requirements of various pyrolysis techniques, the unpredictability of biomass, and the possibility of contamination. Even though our understanding of biochar is growing rapidly, there are still engineering challenges throughout the manufacturing process. Improving this material's harvesting and management is the first step to enable biochar producers to more effectively obtain feedstock while advancing additional land-management goals (Han et al., 2018). Another major issue is designing new biochar production techniques that outperform existing systems economically, reduce net methane (CH₄) and soot emissions, and boost C efficiency. Facilities of a moderate to large scale are frequently more economical to operate (Han, et al., 2018). Research on small-scale biochar producers indicates a significant need for improved solutions (Groot et al., 2018). Making biochar application techniques better for soils is a third significant engineering problem. One part of this effort is figuring out which physical forms of biochar, including particle size, dry solid, or aqueous slurry, are suitable for each application environment. The application of biochar, alone or in combination with other inputs such as compost or fertilizer, is a second factor to consider (Page-Dumroese et al., 2016). Creating new opportunities to produce multiple value-added products from gaseous, solid, and liquid outputs is another significant technical challenge (Lehmann & Joseph, 2024). Syngas is a crucial product that is rarely utilized outside centralized facilities, and its development is advancing new goods using biochar and biooil, as well as heat. This heat is either used to dry feedstocks or captured as power in certain biochar systems (such as boilers that produce steam), while in other systems, it is just discharged because heat capture is not cost-effective.

5.2 Economic challenges in biochar production

For biochar systems, economic feasibility remains a major obstacle (Sohi et al., 2010; Lehmann & Joseph, 2015). The costs of buying feedstocks, financing, operating, and exporting feedstocks and products, as well as the revenue streams from energy and biochar products, climate offsets, and renewable energy subsidies, constitute key elements influencing economic feasibility. Now, it is more profitable to convert biomass into bioenergy. This is equally true of the relative economics of fast-pyrolysis systems, which produce less biochar and more bioenergy than slow-pyrolysis systems (Brown, et al., 2011). However, when comparing biochar and bioenergy systems in terms of their capacity to slow climate change, the scenario is inverted (Woolf et al., 2010). The main concerns influencing economic viability can be roughly divided into two categories: increasing market value or further lowering manufacturing costs.

High feedstock procurement costs will drastically affect the feasibility of biochar production operations. Depending on the scale of production, feedstock costs can account for 40% to 75% of the total cost of producing biochar (Shackley et al., 2015). Optimizing operational logistics is necessary to minimize feedstock costs. Labor, logistics, and capital all affect the cost of generating biochar at scales up to about 100,000 BD tons of feedstock per year. For every dry ton of fuel input per hour, the cost of thermal equipment and emissions control can exceed \$1 million (Wilson & Miles, n.d.).

5.3 Policy gaps for biochar production

Locations that generate biochar may need air permits, stormwater permits, waste discharge permits, solid waste permits, restricted-use licenses, and other environmental assessments. Both stationary and mobile operations must adhere to all relevant regulatory

standards. The size and location of the facility, the operational characteristics of the technology, the feedstock's composition, origin, and classification, the site's land-use zoning, the governing jurisdiction, and the environmental circumstances will all affect the specific regulatory requirements. The expense and complexity of air emissions permits can be a significant obstacle to the wider adoption of biochar production, even though a thorough examination of all licensing issues was outside the workshop's purview. Because of the numerous new technologies, varying air quality concerns, varying state legislation, and other considerations, tribal, state, and local governments have diverse procedures for authorizing biochar units (Kong, et al., 2014). Even though biochar improves air quality for those considering employing biochar production units to replace open burning in forestry and agriculture, the required regulatory process is typically far more complex, expensive, and time-consuming than the open-burning permitting process (Miller & Lemieux, 2007). The regions they would operate in, how frequently they would travel, and how easily the authorities could contact them for inspections have also raised concerns. In some locations, obtaining land-use permission can be challenging. To address these issues and develop regulatory frameworks appropriate to their scope and purpose, while also maintaining air quality in the regions where they operate, long-term legislative initiatives may be required.

A comprehensive policy and regulatory approach that covers air quality, wildfire risk reduction, forest product availability, ecological benefits, and management is necessary to support an economical biochar and bioenergy process that uses unmerchantable wood to produce viable products. But creating such persuasive policy tools will require a sustained, coordinated effort (Pierson et al., 2024).

6. FUTURE OPPORTUNITIES IN THE BIOCHAR PRODUCTION AND UTILIZATIONS

6.1 Innovations in the field of biochar production technology

The advancement of production techniques is one of the most fascinating aspects of biochar technology. New methods that improve efficiency, scalability, and environmental benefits are being developed to supplement traditional biochar manufacturing, which mostly involves pyrolysis of organic waste. Thanks to advancements like gasification and low-temperature pyrolysis, it is now possible to produce biochar with the ideal qualities for uses such as improving soil, storing carbon, and even purifying water (Anon 2024). The technology for producing biochar has advanced significantly with the advent of portable kiln prototypes. Particularly noteworthy are developments in decentralized, portable biochar production systems, which provide smallholder farmers with scalable, affordable options. A study by Santos et al. (2025) attempts to describe biochar produced from leguminous and non-leguminous crop residues, using a variety of production techniques that consider these developments. Redesigning and creating a vertically portable kiln using the direct updraft technique is part of this. Prior studies have focused on elemental and proximate studies of biochar made in kilns, but there hasn't been a thorough characterization. In addition to calculating stable carbon and heavy metal contamination, the current study's characterization of biochar using sophisticated techniques, including Electron Microscopy-Electron Dispersive X-ray (SEM-EDX), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), has provided greater insight into its characteristics. In addition to offering practical insights into its cost-effective, decentralized production using portable kilns for sustainable agriculture, the authors have sought to contribute to fundamental research on biochar.

6.2 Future policy recommendations

A biochar policy framework should address several topics, including R&D financing, non-financial assistance, and financial incentives. It should also define general product criteria for biochar, acknowledge soil as a resource, and address the monetization of environmental advantages. According to Pourhashem et al. (2019), three types of programs can help with biochar production: financial support for research and development, non-financial policy support, and commercial financial incentives. Developing a widely recognized set of criteria for biochar products, recognizing soil as a resource through national preservation laws, and strengthening legislation that permits monetizing cost savings and environmental benefits are among the main recommendations. The financial gap between those who pay for land management reforms and those who benefit from them can be lessened by well-crafted legislation. Creating systems that enable farmers to be paid for ecosystem services resulting from their improved land management practices is one way to achieve this. This can be achieved through markets that monetize ecosystem services as property rights (Jim Blackburn, 2016).

For the right industries, this strategy can internalize the costs and gains of better land management, making biochar a competitive commodity for buyers. Furthermore, a well-crafted policy incentive specifically for the biochar sector can catalyze the development of reliable production techniques, future financial viability, and market penetration for emerging biochar companies (Jirka & Tomlinson, 2015). Given its potential longer-term advantages, one could argue that the "infant industry" thesis applies to biochar (Black et al., 2012). For instance, industry growth can be supported by government financial incentives such as tax credits, loan guarantees, or subsidies.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Biochar has become a groundbreaking solution for addressing significant problems related to climate change mitigation, sustainable agriculture, and the circular economy. Biochar, which is made from food, animal, and agricultural waste, improves soil health,

sequesters carbon, and lowers greenhouse gas emissions, providing a holistic approach to waste valorization. Feedstock type, pyrolysis conditions, and application techniques all affect its effectiveness; customized approaches are crucial for optimizing results. The implementation of biochar is hindered by technical, financial, and regulatory issues that require standardization, legislative support, and further research, despite its environmental benefits and potential role in carbon markets. To reach its full potential, biochar must be integrated into closed-loop agricultural models, scaled decentralized production systems, and made more economically viable. With continued innovation and policy alignment, biochar could play a significant role in global efforts to advance regenerative agriculture and climate resilience.

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9. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article.

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